

A Study of Morbidity Pattern of Patients Attending a Rural Clinic of Coastal Karnataka

Sanjay Kini¹, Rahul Hegde², N Udaya Kiran³

¹Assistant Professor, ²Post-graduate Student, ³Professor and Head, Department of Community Medicine, KS Hegde Medical Academy, Mangalore

ABSTRACT

The pattern and distribution of morbidities of the people along with their age, sex and in different seasons of the year has been attempted by the study. Data for one year was obtained from routine consultation and recorded on a pre-designed morbidity sheets from out-patient attendance of Peripheral health centre, Farangipet, under the department of Community Medicine, KSHEMA, Mangalore. Only new patients were taken into account. The case rate was reported higher for the advanced age group (>45 years). The percentage of female consultations (43.0 per 1000 populations) was more than that of males (35.7 per 1000 populations). Respiratory & GIT diseases still contributed the major proportion of morbidities in both sexes. Consultation rate shows increasing trend as age advanced. The attendance rate for most of the illnesses was observed more in rainy season.

Keywords: Morbidity pattern, Rural Clinic, Coastal Karnataka.

INTRODUCTION

The nature of health is multidimensional and measurement of it is difficult and indicators like morbidity, mortality and disability are the one which are used to capture the status of health. It is easy to collect data on morbidity but measurement is difficult without a bias which is subjective. Various researchers at the national and local levels have done a bulk of research for standardization of definitions of morbidity¹⁻¹⁰. A measurable indicator of well-being is morbidity, or physical and mental illness which is increasingly being recognized⁹. Important facts have been revealed by studies pertaining to morbidity. Apart from informing about the health status of various groups it also helps in identifying the extent and type of prevalent morbidities which helps in providing vital feed-back for setting priorities in health services reforms. The aim of this study was to find the morbidity pattern in Farangipet, a village in rural field practice area of department of Community Medicine, KS Hegde Medical Academy (KSHEMA), Mangalore.

MATERIAL & METHOD

The study was undertaken by the department of

Community Medicine, KSHEMA. The department runs 20 peripheral health centres in various villages namely Bailur, Nitte, Sringeri, Subramanya, Bengre, Farangipet, Natekal, Sasihitlu, Mundkur, Talipady, Mulki, Hejamadi and Kadri. In the present study, the morbidity pattern was seen through Out Patients Department (OPD) approach in a span of one year in the rural health centre of Farangipet. The analysis was done on the basis of new patients only; if the same patient came for consultation for more than one time for a particular illness then he/she may be considered once. The OPD and the health care services delivered through a team of departmental members including faculty, post graduate residents, medical social workers and interns. As per the norms laid down at rural health centre, OPD services are run on every working day. Awareness generation camps, surveillance, referral and follow up are carried out in this area. All the diagnosed diseases were classified in to broad categories on the basis of physiological systems and a separate head was given for generalized pain, weakness, fever, and headache. Morbidity pattern was analysed from the OPD attendance register. Ethical consent was obtained from institutional ethical committee of KSHEMA.

RESULTS

There were a total of 3101 patients attending the OPD in a span of one year. Table 1 shows the distribution of cases according to the age and sex of the patients. It was found that age of the people was significantly associated with sex ($p < 0.001$).

Table-1: Distribution of OPD Patient Consultations according to the Age & Sex of Persons

Age (in years)	Sex								
	Male			Female			Both		
	No of people	No of consultation		No of people	No of consultation		No of people	No of consultation	
	No	No	%	No	No	%	No	No	%
<5	230	76	33.0	201	81	40.2	431	157	36.4
5-15	422	196	46.4	371	111	29.9	793	307	38.7
15-45	757	201	26.5	761	244	36.3	1428	445	31.1
>45	238	115	48.3	211	190	90.0	449	305	67.9
Total	1647	588	35.7	1454	626	43.0	3101	1214	39.1

Gender wise distribution of various types of cases is depicted in Table 2. The overall difference in the morbidity between males and females was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Table-2: Distribution of Reported Cases of different Diseases according to Sex

Morbidity	Sex								
	Male (N=1647)			Female (N=1454)			Total (N=3101)		
	Reported cases		Case rate	Reported cases		Case rate	Reported cases		Case rate
	No	%		No	%		No	%	
GIT-diseases	67	11.3	40.6	72	11.4	49.5	139	11.4	44.8
Respiratory diseases	113	19.1	68.6	106	16.9	72.9	219	17.9	70.6
Eye diseases	24	4.0	14.5	29	4.6	19.9	53	4.3	17.0
ENT diseases	17	2.8	10.3	11	1.7	7.5	28	2.3	9.0
Skin diseases	49	8.3	29.7	36	5.7	24.7	85	6.9	27.4
Bone & joints diseases	59	10.0	35.8	79	12.5	54.3	138	11.3	44.5
Nutritional deficiency	33	5.5	20.0	50	7.9	34.3	83	6.8	26.7
Injury & accidents	60	10.1	36.4	20	3.1	13.7	80	6.5	25.7
Parasitic & infectious diseases	28	4.7	17.0	19	3.0	13.0	47	3.8	15.1
Fever	73	12.3	44.3	114	18.1	78.4	187	15.3	60.3
Headache	19	3.2	11.5	21	3.3	14.4	40	3.2	12.8
Others*	48	8.1	29.1	70	11.1	48.1	118	9.6	38.0
Total	590	100.0	358.2	627	100.0	431.2	1217	100.0	392.4

Case rate= per 1,000 population, $p < 0.001$; * "Others" includes diseases mainly the lower abdominal pain, chest pain, U.T.I, weakness, low backache etc.

Table 3 shows the distribution of reported cases of different diseases according to the age of the people. The difference of morbidity pattern in attendance rate among the age groups was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Table-3: Distribution of reported cases of different diseases according to the age of the people

Morbidity	Age (in years)								Total
	Up to 5 (n=430)		(5-15) (n=793)		(15-45) (n=1429)		>45 (n=449)		
	Reported cases	Case rate	Reported cases	Case rate	Reported cases	Case rate	Reported cases	Case rate	
GIT-diseases	20	4.6	36	4.5	55	3.8	28	6.2	139
Respiratory diseases	29	6.7	44	5.5	67	4.6	79	17.5	219
Eye diseases	7	1.6	14	1.7	12	0.8	20	4.4	53
ENT diseases	5	1.1	14	1.7	5	0.3	4	0.8	28
Skin diseases	21	4.8	36	4.5	19	1.3	9	2.0	85
Bone & joints diseases	4	0.9	15	1.8	56	3.9	63	14.0	138
Nutritional deficiency	16	3.7	19	2.3	38	2.6	10	2.2	83
Injury & accidents	7	1.6	37	4.6	27	1.8	9	2.0	80
Parasitic & infectious diseases	13	3.0	16	2.0	12	0.8	6	1.3	47
Fever	30	6.9	47	5.9	72	5.0	38	8.4	187
Headache	1	0.2	9	1.1	19	1.3	11	2.4	40
Others*	5	1.1	20	2.5	63	4.4	30	6.6	118
Total	158	36.7	307	38.7	445	31.8	307	68.3	1217

Case rate= per 100 population * "Others" includes diseases mainly the lower abdominal pain, chest pain, U.T.I, weakness, low backache etc

Distribution of reported cases in different seasons is depicted in table 4.

Table-4: Distribution of the reported cases of diseases in different seasons

Morbidity	Season						Total	
	Summer		Rainy		Winter			
	Reported cases		Reported cases		Reported cases		No	%
	No	%	No	%	No	%		
GIT-diseases	69	49.6	40	28.8	30	21.6	139	100.0
Respiratory diseases	71	32.4	65	29.6	83	38	219	100.0
Eye diseases	24	45.2	15	28.3	14	26.5	53	100.0
ENT diseases	7	25.0	11	39.2	10	35.8	28	100.0
Skin diseases	17	20.0	40	47.0	28	33.0	85	100.0
Bone & joints diseases	42	30.4	38	27.5	58	42.0	138	100.0
Nutritional deficiency	26	31.3	35	42.1	22	26.6	83	100.0
Injury & accidents	27	33.8	23	28.7	30	37.5	80	100.0
Parasitic & infectious diseases	18	38.3	15	31.9	14	29.8	47	100.0
Fever	53	28.4	80	42.8	54	28.8	187	100.0
Headache	12	30.0	14	35.0	14	35.0	40	100.0
Others*	41	34.7	36	30.6	41	34.7	118	100.0
Total	407	33.4	412	33.9	398	32.7	1217	100.0

DISCUSSION

It was observed that patients reported for consultations in OPD were more in age group of (>45) years (67.9%) in comparison to other age groups. This finding differs from the other studies, one done by Singh¹¹, reported maximum attendance in under five and age group of (15-24) years, while Dutta and Kale¹² observed maximum attendance in the age group of (25-44) years and minimum in age group of (15-25) years.

Gender wise analysis reveals that the consultations were higher for females than males in each age group except in the age group of (5-15). It was almost doubled in age group (>45) years. It may be because of the gynecological complains in females other than their routine consultation. Similar findings have been established in other studies done by Rao et.al¹³, Mustafa¹⁴, Madhiwala et.al¹⁵ in India and Belcher et.al¹⁶ in Ghana. The out-patient attendance according to the total population was shown that the annual consultation rate was (392.4 per 1000 population) in the study area. However in another study done by Singh¹¹ reported unusual higher rate i.e., 99/100 population in the same area, more for females than males. This could be due to the overall socio-economic improvement and increase in the number of other health facilities in the area. Moreover, the age of the people was found significantly associated with sex ($p<0.001$).

It was found that out of total reported cases at OPD, Respiratory diseases (17.9%) followed by Fever (15.3 %), GIT diseases (11.4%) and Bone and Joint problems contributed the principle cause of morbidity in the study population. The similar pattern was also reported in different studies^{17,11,18} and NCEAR⁶. The Skin diseases (6.9%) and nutritional deficiency (6.8%) was found to be the next important problems among different reported morbidities. Prevalence of respiratory diseases was found more among males (19.1%) than female population (16.9%). Among females, complain of fever formed the most common disease (18.2%) followed by Respiratory diseases, Bone and Joint related diseases and GIT diseases. The case rate per 1000 population for most of illnesses was found higher for females than male population with the exception in cases of injuries & accidents, ENT, skin and parasitic related diseases. This observation is in accordance with the findings of Pandey¹⁹ and Singh¹¹. The overall difference of

morbidity in attendance between male and female was found to be statistically significant ($p<0.001$).

In all age groups except in the group (>45) year, maximum people consulted the OPD with the complain of fever. In these groups, case rate was also found higher for respiratory and GIT diseases followed by bone and Joint and skin diseases. As the age advanced (> 45 years age- group), people with respiratory diseases and illnesses associated with Bone and Joint reported the maximum attendance in the OPD, consistent with the findings of Seal et al¹⁸, while Pandey¹⁹ observed the higher rates in age group of 1-4 years. However morbidities like nutritional deficiency, parasitic infections and skin diseases were more among under five year age group in comparison to other age groups. The differences of morbidity pattern in attendance rate among the age groups was found to be statistically significant ($p<0.001$). For most of the morbidities registered in OPD, case rate per 1000 populations were found more in rainy season followed by the winter season. In the present study, the diseases like GIT, Eye and Parasitic & Infectious are more common in summer while ENT, Skin, Fever and Nutritional deficiency related diseases reported maximum attendance during rainy season. Respiratory diseases are more prominent (around 38%) during winter than summer (32.4%) and rainy season (29.6%). Also, Bone & Joint related diseases and Injuries & accidents were found more during winter season.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

Considering the increase in life expectancy and the importance of health of elderly population and as a result, the existence of higher case rate in the present study, periodical screening or special clinics is required for them. Opportunity should not be missed to see the children less than five age-groups coming with mother in ANC clinics. For the prevention and control of various prevalent infectious diseases, especially GIT and respiratory diseases, more emphasis should be given on environmental sanitation, personal hygiene, provision of safe water and health education.

Source of Funding: None

Conflict of Interest: None

Acknowledgement: Nil

REFERENCES

1. Gumber A, Berman P. "Measurement and Pattern of Morbidity and Utilization of Health Services: A review of Health Survey in India", Working paper no. 65, Gujrat Institute of Development and Research, 1995.
2. Kumar BG. "Low Mortality and High Morbidity Reconsidered", Population & development review, 19(1), 103-21, 1993.
3. Murray CJL, Chen LC. "Underlying Morbidity Change", Population & development review, 18(3), 481-503, 1992.
4. National Family Health Survey, (NFHS-2), 1998-99, India, Mumbai: International Institute for Population Sciences, October, 2000.
5. National Family Health Survey, (NFHS-3), 2005-06, India, Mumbai: International Institute for Population Sciences.
6. NCEAR. "House Survey of Medical Care", National Council for Applied Economic Research, New Delhi, 1992.
7. Niyogi AK, Trivedi DH, Pateli YI, 1969, "Longitudinal survey of morbidity and needs of a PHC", Indian Journal of Preventive and Social Medicine, 1969.
8. NSS. Morbidity and Utilization of Medical Services", NSS 42nd Round (1986- 87) in Savekshana, no 52; Volume XV, no 4, April-June, 92 Govt. of India, 1992.
9. Shariff A. "Health Transition in India", Working Paper No. 57, NCEAR; New Delhi, 1995.
10. Vaidyanthan A. "An Assessment of Nutritional and Health Status", Discussion paper No.3, UNDP research project, CDS, 1995.
11. Singh. IJ. "A Study of Morbidity Pattern in a Rural Community", Health and Population 2 (3): 193- 206, 1979.
12. Dutta SP and Kale PV. "An Observational Research Study in Primary Medical Care in Pondicherry", Indian Journal of Preventive and Social Medicine, 1, No. 2, 1969.
13. Rao NSN, Marwah SM, Tiwari IC et al. "Disabilities, Morbidity and Mortality in a Community Development Block" , Indian Journal of Medical Sciences, 513-520, 1973.
14. Mustafa SSA. "Study of Morbidity & Health Expenditure in a Rural Health Centre", Chiraigaon, India M. Comm.H. Dissertation, 1977.
15. N Madhiwala, A Jesani. "Morbidity among Women in Mumbai city Impact of Work & Environment", Economic and Political Weekly, vol. xxxii, No. 43, pp 38-44, 1997.
16. Belcher DW, Wurapa, FK et al. "A household Morbidity Survey in Rural Africa", International Journal of Epidemiology, 5, 113-119, 1976.
17. Dutta Jyant Kumar and Banerjee RR. "Morbidity Pattern of Out Patient's Attendance", Indian Journal of Paediatrics, 37: 267, 1970.
18. Seal SC et al. "General Health Survey of Talcher Community Development Block", Orissa, Director General of Health Services, New Delhi, 1958.
19. Pandey JN. "A Case Study of Health Culture of Ledhupur Village", Thesis submitted for the degree of MD, Department of Preventive and Social Medicine, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, 1977.